

D3.2 Requirements for professional teacher training for innovative technologies and needs workshop methodologies

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D3.2 – Requirements for professional teacher training for innovative technologies and needs workshop methodologies

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is Deliverable D3.2 connected to task 3.3 in the 3rd work package and is part of MS3 of the LEA project. The leader of the work package is Otto-von-Guericke-University, who also compiled the deliverable. Task 3.3 aims to detect the barriers which prevent the use of learning technology in schools as well as the competencies needed by students and teachers.

1.1 Purpose of the report

The use of digital learning technology has great potential for the school sector. It can promote individual and lifelong learning via the use of special learning environments and prepare content in a form that would be difficult or impossible to implement with conventional means. This is accompanied by new methodological approaches that enable or simplify forms of collaborative work.

Nevertheless, the implementation of learntech in schools is not always possible without issues. There are certain barriers, both on the part of teachers and students, which must be identified and overcome. For this reason, the full potential of learntech for use in schools often cannot be fully exploited. Furthermore, when procuring innovative learning technology, it is important to recognize these barriers for a successful implementation in schools.

- A** Against this background, the following questions arose, to which a contribution was made in Task 3.3
- B** What skills do students/teachers need to use digital teaching and learning tools?
- C** What are the barriers for students/teachers when using digital teaching and learning tools?

Based on the analysis of the necessary competences and barriers of students and teachers, this deliverable aims to give procurers an idea

which requirements need to be included into learning technology procurement to master the challenge and make the adoption of innovative solutions a success.

1.2 Approach

In order to answer the questions raised, a quantitative survey for students and teachers was developed and conducted as part of Task 3.3. The experience and the network from the IMAILE test phase were used to some extent. The aim of this survey is in particular to ask teachers and pupils about the necessary competencies.

In addition, guideline-based interviews were conducted to explore possible barriers that students and teachers have when using learntech. This approach was chosen because the barriers to use can be many and varied. Therefore it is much more difficult to gather significant data by means of an itemised survey.

The development of the survey and the key questions was initiated by the 6-3-5 brainwriting method, which allowed all LEA partners to provide valuable input for the creation of the questions.

2. REQUIREMENTS AND BARRIERS FOR A SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN SCHOOLS

There is a great amount of innovative technology for schools available on the market for many years, but the acceptance and usage in schools in Europe is still very low. In the EU project IMAILE, the current situation has been analyzed in a state of the art report ([1]), to find out what teachers and students really need in order to incorporate ICT solutions and tools into the classroom with the result, that a significant amount of research and development is required to achieve an acceptable fit between required features and implemented features in the solutions. The aim of the IMAILE project was to support the development of customized solutions. The LEA project takes the next step, looking to identify the requirements and barriers for a successful implementation of these innovative learning technologies in schools.

Studies show, that there are common factors, functioning as enablers or barriers of ICT integration (see [2]–[4]). Typical barriers are mostly missing resources or opportunities, like

- the lack of hardware,
- the lack of appropriate software materials,
- the lack of technical support,
- the lack of in-service training for teachers,
- the lack of teacher competencies to use certain software
- insufficient financing
- the lack of cooperation among teachers among one or more schools
- shortage of time.

Enablers are, corresponding to the barriers, for instance

- the allocation of more budget,
- the allocation of specific units for peer support,

- the allocation of support offices and personnel for teachers, especially technical support staff
- the offering of higher quality pre-service training for ICT for teachers
- the provision of resources such as time for teachers to learn about innovations in ICT
- a motivation model for teachers to implement innovations.

Lim and Khine ([4]) suggest three strategies to manage the barriers: the professional development of teachers, provision of time for teachers' professional development and curricular development, and technical, administrative and pedagogical support for teachers. These strategies can be supported by a better knowledge about the teachers point of view and what they see as barriers and as requirements to overcome them. For the participating procurers in this project, we created the questionnaires to achieve this knowledge.

For a successful implementation, the required competencies not only of the teachers, but also of the students needs to be taken into consideration. A lack of their competencies will become another barrier for the use of learning environments by the teacher. We created questionnaires for students, too, to get this information.

This study has a special focus on required competencies to use personal learning environments.

3. METHODOLOGY

Section 1 of this report deals with the two research questions to be answered in D3.2 task 3.3. Each question was again divided into two sub-questions for systematic answer, see Table 1 below.

Table 1: Research questions D3.2 task 3.3

Nr.	Nr.	Research Question
1	1	What competencies do pupils need when using digital teaching and learning tools?
	2	What are the barriers that pupils face when using digital teaching and learning tools?
2	3	What competencies do teachers need when using digital teaching and learning tools?
	4	What are the barriers teachers face when using digital teaching and learning tools?

To answer these complex questions, a qualitative approach using a web-based survey tool (limesurvey, described in Section 3.3) was chosen. Since networking with the project partners in Germany, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Spain and Hungary made it possible to reach many potential test persons, a number of 300 was targeted for the interviewed teachers and 1000 for the interviewed pupils.

The content of the questionnaire was constructed in several steps. In advance, possible categories and subcategories were identified using the 6-5-3 method (described in Section 3.1). Afterwards, a first draft was discussed and a pretest was conducted within the framework of the Long Night of Science at the Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg. From the findings of this test run, a first optimized version was created, which was sent to the project partners in order to carry out further content and structural optimizations. After the second optimization phase, a final version was

created, which was released for translation into the respective national languages by the project partners. Finally, a country-specific (language-specific) questionnaire version in limesurvey was created from the translated questionnaires for each project partner and sent.

3.1 6-3-5 Brainwriting

In order to obtain a questionnaire that is as usable as possible for questioning students and teachers, ideas and suggestions for possible questions, categories and thematic priorities should first be developed. The 6-3-5 method (see Annex 1: Template for the 6-3-5 Brainwriting) was used for this purpose. Among creativity techniques, this is a brainwriting technique that promotes a problem-solving process for creating new (unusual) ideas in a group of people. This creativity technique is suitable for finding ideas based on concrete questions on challenges of simple to medium complexity. Also 6-3-5 is well suited for idea enrichment. The 6-3-5 method was named after the ideal of six participants, each of whom produces three initial ideas and then develops five times three initial ideas of other participants or ideas derived from them.

The method is applied in the following steps:

- Step 1:** Each participant receives a prepared worksheet (see annex 1). The worksheet contains the question to be answered in the header, as well as the fields for the ideas. The worksheet consists of three columns and several rows.
- Step 2:** Each of the participants now writes three ideas and enters them in the fields on the first line.
- Step 3:** At the end of the time period, the worksheets are passed clockwise to the nearest neighbor.
- Step 4:** Each participant should now try to take up, supplement or further develop the ideas already mentioned on the sheet he has. He enters his three new or refined ideas in the next free line.

The advantage of the 6-3-5 method is that the participants can give and take direct feedback. In addition, many ideas are generated in a relatively short time and are written down. This tool encourages equal opportunity

ideation between all participants, regardless of their standing within the team or organizations.

3.2 Quantative Survey

Following the execution of the 6-3-5 method, the results were summarized, evaluated and categorized. Based on a corresponding research on barriers and necessary competences for the use of learntech in schools (see chapter 2), the items for the survey of teachers and students were developed.

The content of the sections is described in more detail below. The questionnaire is divided into thematic sections for teachers and pupils. The teachers find the following sections in their questionnaire, shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Sections of teachers questionnaires

Nr.	Section
I	Demographic Data
II	Barriers to be expected on the teachers' side
III	Expected, necessary competences of teachers
IV	Barriers to be expected on the pupils' side
V	Expected, necessary competences of the pupils
VI	Expected, necessary technical equipment of the school

The following categories have been identified for the barriers/competencies of students/teachers:

Barriers (Students)

Category	Subcategories
Family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptance of learntech within the family • Informations for parents on how learntech is used in school

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competencies using (learn)tech within the family • Time constraints from parents on how much time children are allowed to spend using learntech • Equipment at home
Teaching Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competencies of teachers • Dedicated time to use learntech in class • Informations for teachers on how learntech is supposed to be used in school • Motivation of teachers on how to use learntech
Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informations for students on how learntech is supposed to be used in school • Exercises on how to use learntech • Competencies of students and soft skills • Support through teachers and parents • Support of different learning types • Availability of digital learning material • Interest/motivation to use learntech
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication with all involved parties (teachers/parents/students) • Support for students and teachers • Available equipment and infrastructure
Learning Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of use

Competencies (Students)

Category Subcategories

Personal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest/motivation to use learntech • Empathy • Classical cultural competencies (reading, writing) • Ability to concentrate • Knowledge of own learning type
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to use different devices
Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills to use digital technology • Ability to create digital artifacts (videos, podcasts,...) • Handling data/files • Ability to use different tools

Barriers (Teachers)

Category Subcategories

- | | |
|----------|--|
| Personal | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivation/ability to implement learntech in lessons • Fear of loss of authority in class • Fear of loss of content due to software restrictions • Teacher training for learntech • Time needed for implementation of learntech software |
| Hardware | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality and number of available equipment in school • Possible problems with BYOD (different operating systems) • Performance of hardware |
| Software | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge/information about learntech software • Learntech software new for teachers • Frequent updates |
| Lessons | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal interaction with students |

Competencies (Teachers)

Category Subcategories

- | | |
|----------|--|
| Personal | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT skills (using hardware and software) • Motivation for continuous further education • Motivation to experiment with new possibilities • Open mindedness towards current / new technology and methods • Time Capacity • Contact/Exchange with colleagues • Contact/Exchange with parents |
| Hardware | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence in using available hardware • Strategies for troubleshooting in case of problems |
| Software | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence in using available software • Strategies for troubleshooting in case of problems • Accounts with relevant rights within school IT infrastructure |
| Lessons | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility to monitor the students learning process • Interdisciplinary use of learning material • methodical and didactical competencies • Openness in own lessons (transparency for students, other teachers and parents) |

Technical Equipment

Category Subcategories

General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constantly available support • Local IT expert in schools • Online materials for further education
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate internet connection • Local server/cloud • Support • Replacement devices • Mobile devices (Laptop, Tablet)
Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device independency • Ensured data privacy • Online/offline versions • Safe and quick access to materials

From these categories the items for the survey were subsequently obtained. Since there is no certainty about the causality of the variables for the answers to the questions formulated at the beginning and thus no separation into dependent and independent variables is possible, the study was created as a explorative cross-sectional study. The questions for teachers and students can be found in annex 2 and 3, respectively.

At the beginning of the questionnaire, teachers are asked to indicate their gender, the country they work in and the type of school they teach at. These data are of great importance for the following evaluation in order to be able to highlight corresponding results in correlation to gender and country-specific differences and/or similarities.

In Section II, teachers are confronted with questions and possible answers aimed at highlighting possible barriers to the use of digital teaching and learning tools. The evaluation of the data of this section is used as a first basis for the recommendations for action. The questions in Section II are conceived in a multi-perspective way in order to reveal findings for possible

barriers in the areas of lesson preparation, lesson follow-up, lesson execution and administration of the corresponding school infrastructure (existing software and hardware and support of the IT infrastructure). Among other things, this will include questions on the frequency of use of corresponding terminal devices and the question of explicit expected changes in teaching with the use of digital teaching and learning tools. Furthermore, this section will highlight the subjects in which digital tools are already being used. In the subsequent evaluation of the questionnaire, it is possible to deduce, among other things, for which subjects there is potential for use.

In Section III, the teachers are asked about the expected necessary competences which they need/ should develop/ possess themselves in order to be able to efficiently prepare lessons with the help of digital teaching and learning tools, to carry them out in a goal-oriented manner and to follow them up accordingly in a reflective way. The evaluation of these data takes on a further central importance since identified competencies can be directly derived here

In sections IV and V there will be a change of perspective. Teachers will be guided by expected barriers to the use of digital teaching and learning tools on the part of pupils and by expected necessary competences which pupils should show/develop in order to be able to use digital teaching and learning tools in lessons in a targeted and efficient manner. In the evaluation, the findings can be compared with the pupils' statements on barriers and competences. In this way, possible differences and similarities can be identified and the results of both sides (teachers and pupils) can be sharpened for the recommendation for action.

The last section of the questionnaire for teachers asks questions about technical equipment in schools. This is not only an analysis of the current situation, but also a survey of the expected necessary equipment of the IT infrastructure in schools where digital teaching and learning tools are to be

used in class. In combination with the findings of the evaluation of the expected barriers and competences from the areas II and III, an overview of the equipment of the schools will be compiled. This data is evaluated in D3.4 and will therefore be neglected in this report.

The students' questionnaire is divided into similar sections, see Table 3 below.

Table 3: Sections of students questionnaires

Nr.	Section
I	Demographic Data
II	Barriers to be expected on the side of pupils at home
III	Barriers to be expected on the side of pupils at school
IV	Expected, necessary competences on the pupils' side
V	Expected, necessary technical equipment of the school

A major difference is that learners are not asked about barriers and competences on the teacher side.

The first section deals with gender, country of origin and class level of the pupils. From this, gender-specific and country-specific statements on barriers and competences on the side of the pupils can be derived.

In contrast to the sections of the questionnaire for teachers, additional questions are asked. Pupils are asked in Section II to describe their usage behaviour of communication technology devices in terms of the number of hours. A further point of this section is the question of assistance by or also for the legal guardians with possible problems/tasks with digital terminals.

In Section III, pupils are asked questions about possible barriers to the use of digital teaching and learning tools in schools that they expect to encounter. The focus of this section is on current empirical data on the previous or current use of digital terminal devices/ digital teaching and learning tools in

school/teaching. In addition, it must be determined whether the pupils consider preparatory information events and preparatory courses to be necessary. The learners are also asked to choose between the increased use of digital teaching and learning aids and the increased use of analogue teaching and learning aids. In particular, knowledge can be gained from the last two questions in order to prevent possible barriers and (further) develop corresponding, necessary competences.

Necessary competences on the side of the pupils are to be identified in Section IV. For this purpose, the learners name skills and abilities in the questionnaire and weight the corresponding selection. Afterwards, a self-assessment of selected skills and abilities in handling hardware and software is carried out. This self-assessment is used in the evaluation to describe the actual status.

In the last section, pupils are asked about the current technical equipment of their school and what they consider to be the necessary equipment for the use of digital teaching and learning tools. Part of this section is the selection of the preferred type of digital devices in the classroom. Students choose between standard devices provided by the school and the Bring Your Own Device (BYOD) approach, according to which each student brings his/her individual and private device into the classroom. Those informations will also be evaluated in D3.4.

Both, the questionnaire for the teachers and the questionnaire for the pupils, contain only closed questions. This was done in particular against the background of efficient evaluability. In this way, it was possible to avoid having to categorise different answers, which would have entailed a considerable increase in effort, above all due to the many languages represented.

Implementation of the questionnaire

Survey Tool

For the implementation of the questionnaire, which was carried out in all countries of the project partners, it was decided to use the free online-based survey tool limesurvey prior to the planning of the questionnaire. The advantages are the hosting on the servers of the Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg and the associated guarantee of compliance with the data protection regulations for surveys at schools. For the usability of the data after completion of the survey, appropriate file formats are available for the evaluation and analysis of the answers. The survey was carried out anonymously and each participant had to agree to the data protection conditions with the first question before the questionnaire could be answered. Furthermore, limesurvey offers many functions during the ongoing survey, such as current data for samples, analyses of specific developments and current figures for completed questionnaires. It was also possible to correct spelling mistakes and typos during the course of the survey. The implementation of the translated questionnaires was significantly simplified by appropriate language settings, so that each project partner received a separate link with the corresponding, country-specific questionnaire. Thus the distribution of the questionnaire to schools and corresponding institutions in the respective countries was possible by email.

Pretest

The publication of the questionnaires was preceded by a pretest in Germany. As part of the Long Night of Science 2018 in Magdeburg (LNDW) two laptops were provided in the classroom of the future in the Faculty of Computer Science on which the visitors carried out the questionnaire. In subsequent discussions with the participants, feedback was given on the comprehensibility of the questions and answers, the use of the survey tool and the content of the questions and answers. The findings of the pre-test were largely incorporated into the initial optimisation of the questionnaire.

The basis for the subsequent, second optimization was given by the project partners themselves. The English version of the questionnaire was made available to the project partners in order to receive broad-based feedback and suggestions for optimisation. Thus an effective instrument was constructed with the conclusion of the second optimization.

The project partners were sent a final English version, which they translated into their national language. The translations represent the final basis for the individual questionnaires for the participating countries.

4. FINDINGS

A complete list of the questions and answers can be found in Annex 2: List of Survey Questions (Teachers) and Annex 3 (students). Detailed results can be found in Annex 4: Answers to Survey Questions (Teachers) and Annex 5: Answers to Survey Questions (Students). This chapter will be a summary of the most relevant results.

4.1 Demographic Data

From the project, six countries participated in the questionnaires. Only few demographic data have been collected (distinction between teacher and student, country of residence, and gender), so the data can be completely anonymized. This is important in order to comply with the rules of the EU GDPR and with the ethical standards of our project.

All in all, we have 1278 data sets, 297 of them are from teachers and 981 from students.

Table 4: Distribution of participants in countries¹

Country	Teacher (rel.)	Pupils (rel.)	TOTAL (rel.)
Germany	73 (24,58%)	570 (58,10%)	643 (50,31%)
Finland	28 (9,43%)	103 (34,68%)	131 (10,25%)
Italy	89 (29,97%)	88 (29,63%)	177 (13,85%)
Portugal	48 (16,16%)	45 (15,15%)	93 (7,28%)
Sweden	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)
Spain	35 (11,78%)	47 (15,82%)	82 (6,42%)
Hungary	24 (8,08%)	128 (43,10%)	152 (11,89%)
TOTAL	297 (100%)	981 (100%)	1278 (100%)

¹ The number shown in parentheses represents the relative share of sample of pupils, teachers and total.

4.2 Research Questions

The results of the survey presented in all countries of the project partners with a total of 1278 completed questionnaires (297 teachers and 981 pupils) are used in the following sections to answer the research questions of the work package D3.2 task 3.3.

What competencies do pupils need when using digital teaching and learning tools?

The competencies for students can be obtained from questions ID15, ID17 and ID18 for teachers, as well as questions IDS09, IDS10, IDS12, IDS13 and IDS14 for students.

90% of the teachers say that there should be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software or learning management systems for students. That means, the ability to use these kind of systems is an additional competence students need to acquire.

78% of the students say that there should be such events for students, and 66% state, that there are such events already in place. These numbers underline how important they are.

Regarding the skills students need to successfully participate in lessons with learning software or learning management systems, the following were mentioned by more than 10% of the teachers:

1. Reading
2. Research on the Internet
3. Writing
4. Editing text on the computer
5. Working in groups
6. Manage data and files
7. Using presentation software
8. Working with a partner

In question ID18, we asked the teachers to rank the skills regarding the importance for the students. The most important skills (rated important and very important) are:

1. Students can securely handle personal data and passwords on the Internet.
2. Students can research and store information on the Internet
3. Students can write and format a text.
4. Students can create a presentation.
5. Students can use different browsers.
6. Students can use browser-based / internet-based software.
7. Students can use different platforms on the Internet.
8. Students can use different multimedia objects (images, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation.

When we now look at the students point of view, the list of skills students think they need to know when using learning software corresponds nicely with the list of what teachers think. Here are the five most important skills for students:

1. Reading
2. Research on the internet
3. Writing
4. Editing text on the computer
5. Working in groups

Then we asked the students to assess their own skills on a scale of very good - good - mediocre - bad. Here are the skills students say they are good or very good at:

1. I can securely handle my personal data and passwords on the internet.
2. I can research and store information on the internet.
3. I can write and format a text.
4. I can use different browsers.

5. I can use different platforms on the internet.
6. I can edit an image.
7. I can use different multimedia objects (pictures, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation.
8. I can create a presentation.

These results show that the students think they are good and very good at the skills teachers rate as very important.

Looking at the average assessment students take for themselves, the worst rating is 2,5, which means better than mediocre and none of the skills they consider as bad (4).

What are the barriers that pupils face when using digital teaching and learning tools?

We didn't ask the students directly what they think are barriers for them. An answer to that question from the students point of view could be obtained from differences between skills students think they need and a lack of competence regarding these skills. Our data show no such difference. If the self-assessment of the students is realistic, than a lack of competence of the students is not a barrier for the successful use of learning technologies.

Another barrier for students could be the lack of technical equipment. Students have been asked what they need to work with learning software in question IDS16 and to specify the equipment of their school in question IDS15. Here students list internet access, computer and mobile devices as most important.

In average, 13,9% of the students say that they have internet access in certain rooms and 9,6% have WLAN for teachers and students.

Computer cabinets are available in 15,6% of the schools and laptops in 11,6%.

12,2% of students say that their school is equipped with interactive whiteboards or displays, which only 11,6% of them think as important.

In general, it is a very low level of technical infrastructure, which is a barrier for a successful usage.

In the question ID16 for teachers, we asked them to list the barriers for students. Here are the five most often mentioned barriers from the teachers point of view:

1. Lack of skills in the use of a computer
2. Lack of information about the use of the learning software for parents
3. Complex software structure
4. Diverse devices (BYOD - Bring your own device)
5. Lack of skills in dealing with internet-based / browser-based software

There is a difference in the assessment of the students' skills, since the teachers list the lack of them as the number 1 barrier, while the students rate most of their skills at least as good.

It is interesting, that the teachers list the information to the parents as crucial and also that the BYOD-method is a barrier for them.

What competencies do teachers need when using digital teaching and learning tools?

The competencies for teachers have been asked for in question ID12 and ID13. First, the teachers should select the skills they need to master in order to use learning software in their classroom, and then they were asked to assess their own skills.

The five most selected skills of the teachers are

1. Doing research on the Internet
2. Using presentation software
3. Editing text on the computer
4. Assisting students with the use of digital terminals

5. Processing images on the computer

They say that “integrating computers/devices in a network” and “managing accounts within a network” are the least important skills.

Since these skills are important when using learning environments, especially personalized systems, other personal should be available to carry out these rather technical tasks. This can also be an important requirement for the design of a systems to make these tasks very easy for teachers and students.

The self-assessment of the teachers has the 2,8 as the worst rating, based on a scale from very good(1)- good(2) - mediocre(3) - bad(4). The best rated skills are the following:

1. I can write and format a text.
2. I can research and store information on the internet
3. I can use different browsers.
4. I can use different platforms on the Internet.
5. I can securely handle my personal data and passwords on the Internet.

They rated their ability to “edit a video” with 2,8 (mediocre) and “I can display data in diagrams” with 2,5, but for all other skills, the average rating is “good” or “very good”. That means that they do have the skills they think are most important.

In question ID09, we asked the teachers what would support them in the use of learning software. The five most selected items are:

1. Exchange with other teachers
2. IT Support (in-school)
3. Cloud with materials
4. Sufficient time for using learning software during school year
5. Support in the execution of lessons by qualified personnel

Also, 90% of the teachers answer in question ID11 that there should be special information events or training hours for teachers, and only 58,7% say

that there are these kind of events already happening at their schools (question ID10).

What are the barriers teachers face when using digital teaching and learning tools?

To get information about the barriers teachers face, we asked them in question ID08, which circumstances they think prevent the successful use of learning software or learning management systems in the classroom. From a list of items, they could select as many items as they wanted. By far the most selected items with over 30% are “hardware problems (failure, malfunction)” and “problems with the Internet”, followed by “software problems” with 11,9%. The other items include expenditure for preparation, carrying out and follow-up for lessons. These are selected by less than 7% of the teachers.

When looking at the barriers, they could be lowered or removed with the items teachers selected as points that would support them (see 5.3). The non-existence of the help listed there can also be seen as a barrier. Among the items, there are some that could be supported via a learning environment, namely the “exchange with other teachers” and the “cloud with materials”. Others are organisational items like “sufficient time for using learning software during school year”, and the rest needs additional resources, like “support in the execution of lessons by qualified personnel” and “IT Support (in-school)”.

5. RESULTS DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis of the necessary competences and barriers of students and teachers, this deliverable aims to give procurers an idea of their needs to master the challenge and make the adoption of innovative solutions a success. When asked to select the skills they need to master in order to use learning software in the classroom, the five most frequently indicated items by the teachers were

1. doing research on the Internet (11.4%)
2. using presentation software (11.1%)
3. editing text on the computer (10.1%)
4. assisting student the use of digital terminals (10.0%)
5. processing images on the computer (9.7%)
6. The least often mentioned items were
7. integrating computers in a network (6.6%)
8. managing accounts within a network (4.6%)

These results show that teachers need skills they can use directly for teaching with digital learning aids/ digital learning software. They want to spend their time on the preparation and execution of the lessons and not for the IT-organisation (management) in the classroom or solving problems with the software or hardware. The five most frequently indicated items that would help teachers are (ID09):

1. exchange with other teachers (17.1%)
2. IT Support (in-school) (16.1%)
3. cloud with materials (14.9%)
4. sufficient time for using learning software during school year (9.3%)
5. support in the execution of lessons by qualified personnel (8.5%)

The least often selected item is IT Support (extern) (6.4%).

So if the teachers need help or support, they want it directly, and not from an external source like a headquarter or a hotline with a ticket system.

For the organisation and preparation of lessons, teachers want an exchange of materials (like worksheets, best-practice-examples...), ideas and experiences.

The next Software or System has to be easy to use for students (see ID16, SQ007). Therefore we need helping systems for students AND teachers with an easy structure, that includes the opportunity for parents to be part of the learning process of their children (see ID16, SQ006).

Extra accounts for parents with analyses function and a platform to communicate with teachers and other parents helps students as well. The system has to support different devices if we want to organise the lessons with BYOD (bring your own device). We need standards for BYOD and support for Hardware and Software, that is in the best case right there in the school.

6. REFERENCES

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Annex 2: List of Survey Questions (Teachers)

QID ²	Full text
01	Are you a teacher or a student?
02	In which country do you work?
03	Please enter your gender.
04	Please indicate the type of school you are teaching at. ³
05	Specify what changes you expect in your lessons through the use of learning software.
06	Specify how often the computer/laptop or mobile devices are used in class each week.
061	Please indicate in which subjects the computer/laptop or mobile devices are used
07	Specify the types of teaching materials you prefer to use.
08	Which circumstances prevent the successful use of learning software / learning management systems in the classroom?
09	Please select the points that would support you in the use of learning software.
10	Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software / learning management systems for teachers?
11	Should there be special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software / learning management systems for teachers?
12	Please select the skills you think you need to master in order to use learning software in your lessons.
13	Please assess your skills in working with the computer.
14	Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software/ learning management systems for students?

² QID - Question Identifier

³ Question different depending on chosen country (QID 02)

15	Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/ learning management systems for students?
16	Select the points you identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/ learning management systems.
17	Specify what skills students need to demonstrate to successfully participate in lessons with learning software/ learning management systems.
18	How important are the following computer skills for students to use learning software?
19	Please indicate the technical equipment your school is equipped with.
20	Please indicate which classroom equipment you need for the use of learning software.
21	Please indicate which type of equipment you prefer.

Annex 3: List of Survey Questions (Students)

QID	Full text
01	Are you a student or a teacher?
s02	In which country do you go to school?
s03	Please enter your gender.
s04	Please indicate what school do you go to. ⁴
s05	Please indicate your grade.
s06	Specify the average number of hours per day you use the following devices at home.
s07	Can your parents help you with problems with these devices?
s08	Indicate how often the computer/ laptop or mobile devices are used in class each week.
s09	Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of new learning software/ learning management systems for students?
s10	Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of new learning software/ learning management systems for students?
s11	Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of new learning software for teachers?
s12	Indicate which learning materials you prefer to use.
s13	What do you need to know to work with learning software?
s14	Please assess your skills in working thing the computer.
s15	Specify the equipment your school is equipped with.
s16	Specify which devices/ equipment you need to work with learning software.
s17	What type of devices do you prefer when using learning software in class?

⁴ Question different depending on chosen country (QID s02)

Annex 4: Answers to Survey Questions (Teachers)

ID05: Specify what changes you expect in your lessons through the use of learning software.

For this question, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID05

Code	Answer
SQ001	Opening of lessons
SQ002	Increased effort for lesson preparation
SQ003	Easier preparation of lesson
SQ004	Redesign of all teaching aids (teaching and learning aids)
SQ005	Use of different methods
SQ006	Increasing the motivation of students
SQ007	Loss of control over the teaching process
SQ008	Digitalisation of teaching
SQ009	Increased effort for class follow-up
SQ010	Loss of authority in the classroom
SQ011	Loss of interaction with students
SQ012	Loss of interaction between students

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID05

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	12,7	5,8	14,2	13,9	NA	21,2	19,8	13,0	14,6	14,1
SQ002	7,8	15,4	3,9	2,2	NA	4,4	4,9	7,4	5,7	6,3
SQ003	10,5	6,7	12,7	16,1	NA	6,2	12,3	9,6	11,9	11
SQ004	9,8	6,7	12,7	16,8	NA	11,5	3,7	11,1	10,6	10,8
SQ005	18,3	21,2	22,1	21,9	NA	23,0	21,0	19,4	21,4	20,7

SQ006	18,6	11,5	24	22,6	NA	23,0	23,5	19,1	21,3	20,5
SQ007	2,9	3,8	0,5	0,7	NA	0,0	0,0	2,2	1,3	1,6
SQ008	7,2	19,2	6,4	4,4	NA	8,8	7,4	9,3	7,6	8,1
SQ009	3,9	2,9	0,5	1,5	NA	1,8	2,5	3,4	1,8	2,3
SQ010	2,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	NA	0,0	1,2	0,9	1,0	1
SQ011	2,9	2,9	1,0	0,0	NA	0,0	1,2	2,5	1,1	1,6
SQ012	3,3	3,8	1,0	0,0	NA	0,0	2,5	2,2	1,8	1,9

Tab X shows the relative frequencies of answers. For this purpose, the absolute number, the ratio of the answers per country and the number of possible answers to the total number of answers of the respective country was determined. From there, the differences between these ratios and the European average were assessed. Fig. X shows the ratings of the individual countries with a difference of more than 10% to the European average. It can be seen that there are significant differences in the individual European countries with regard to the changes in teaching anticipated by teachers through the introduction of digital technologies in schools. It is particularly noticeable that...

- ...the answer most frequently chosen on average in all participating countries, with a range of 4.7%, is by far the most important answer (SQ006: 12.5%, SQ001: 15.4%, SQ003: 9.9%, SQ004: 13.1%).
- ...Finnish teachers rate all possible answers, especially SQ006 (-9.0%) and SQ001 (-8.3%), as clearly below average. There is also a clear difference (+11.1%) in answer SQ008. With 19.2%, this is also the second most frequently selected answer from Finnish teachers.
- ...Spanish (+7.1%) and Hungarian (+5.7%) teachers feel SQ001 to be of above-average importance.
- ...Portuguese teachers consider SQ003 (+5.1%) and SQ004 (+6.0%) to be of above-average importance.
- ...Italy(4%) and Germany (5.9%) have the smallest range in differences to the European average. Finland has the largest range (20.1%). Accordingly, Italian and German teachers in particular tended to choose many answers with similar frequencies, while Finnish teachers tended to choose few answers frequently (SQ005, SQ008).
- ...for Germany, Italy, Portugal and Hungary SQ006 is the most important, for Finland SQ005. Both are equally important for Spanish teachers.

The focus on answers with a European average of more than 10% is based in particular on the significance of these answers, which they reveal, but also on the decreasing significance of the differences in answers for less frequently chosen answers. For example, the least frequently selected answer SQ010 (1%) only received 9 responses. A distinction according to gender does not result in any significant differences.

Fig X: Difference to the total average of the 5 best rated answers in the individual countries in percent

ID06: Specify how often the computer/ laptop or mobile devices are used in class each week.

For question ID06, teachers could choose exactly one of the following possible answers.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID06

Code	Answer
A1	not at all
A2	less than 2 times
A3	between 2 and 4 times
A4	between 4 and 6 times
A5	between 6 and 8 times
A6	more than 8 times

Table X: Distribution of answers to question ID06

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	19,4	3,7	12,5	0,0	NA	6,5	0,0	13,6	8,5	10,0
A2	18,1	11,1	48,8	16,7	NA	6,5	20,8	18,5	28,2	25,2
A3	13,9	37,0	22,5	33,3	NA	29	29,2	16,0	28,2	24,4
A4	15,3	11,1	6,3	13,9	NA	16,1	16,7	16,0	10,6	12,2
A5	15,3	11,1	2,5	5,6	NA	16,1	4,2	13,6	6,4	8,9
A6	18,1	25,9	7,5	30,6	NA	25,8	29,2	22,2	18,1	19,3
AVG*	3,4	3,9	2,6	4,0	NA	4,1	3,9	3,6	3,3	3,4

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included.

Figure X shows the distribution of the entire data set.

Fig X: Relative frequencies of responses from all countries

The data and graph show that half of the respondents use electronic learning tools less than twice a week (25%) or between 2 and 4 times a week (25%). One in ten does not use electronic learning tools at all, about one in five (19%) uses them more than 8 times in class. It can also be stated that Spanish (+0.7 AVG), Portuguese (+0.6) and Hungarian and Finnish (both +0.5) teachers use electronic media more frequently than average in class than Italian (-0.8) teachers. On average, German teachers (+0) use media frequently. In addition, the overall picture shows a peak at A2/A3 and another peak at A6.

A comparison of countries (cf. Fig. X) reveals an even more differentiated picture. If we look again at the differences between the relative frequencies of each answer and each country and the mean value of all respondents (cf. Fig. X), it can be seen that...

- ...Teachers in Germany (+9.4%) report an above-average frequency of not using electronic media at all in their lessons. Teachers in Portugal and Hungary (both -10%) report this with below-average frequency (A1).
- ...Italian teachers (+23.6%) use electronic media 2 to 4 times a week with an above-average frequency (A2). Spanish (-18.7%) and Finnish (-14.1%) teachers in particular use electronic media 2 to 4 times a week well below average.
- ...especially Portuguese teachers (+11.3%) use electronic media more than 8 times a week in class (A6). Italian teachers (-11.8%) rarely use them more than 8 times a week.
- ...the peaks, which result from the consideration of all answers, also exist within the countries (Finland: A3/A6, Italy: A2, Portugal: A3/A6, Spain: A6, Hungary: A3/A6).

Fig X: Comparison of relative frequencies of each country with the mean value

ID061: Please indicate in which subjects the computer/ laptop or mobile devices are used.

For question ID061, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers for question ID061

Code	Answer
SQ001	natural sciences
SQ002	social sciences
SQ003	native language
SQ004	foreign languages
SQ005	arts
SQ006	other

Table X: Distribution of answers for question ID061

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	35,8	28,3	20,9	14,3	NA	20,0	36,0	24,2	27,7	25,2
SQ002	11,9	8,7	6,7	12,9	NA	14,7	16,0	9,2	13,3	10,5
SQ003	13,4	21,7	18,7	25,7	NA	12,0	22,0	18,8	16,2	18,0
SQ004	12,7	17,4	19,1	5,7	NA	14,7	10,0	15,3	13,3	14,7
SQ005	11,2	23,9	13,8	14,3	NA	9,3	14,0	13,4	13,3	13,5
SQ006	14,9	0,0	20,9	27,1	NA	29,3	2,0	19,1	16,2	18,2

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, again differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included. A comparison of countries (see Fig. X) reveals an even more differentiated picture.

Fig X: Comparison between countries and the difference to the mean value

Looking again at the differences between the relative frequencies of each answer and each country and the mean of all respondents (see Fig. X), it can be seen that...

- ...digital teaching and learning tools in science subjects are used above average by German (+10,6%) and Hungarian (+10,8%) teachers, whereas the use of these tools by Italian (-4,3%), Portuguese (-10,9%) and Spanish (-5,2%) teachers is below average.

- ...in humanities subjects, digital teaching and learning tools are used above average by Portuguese, Spanish and Hungarian teachers. The answers of the Italian teachers are slightly below average.
- ...digital teaching and learning tools are increasingly used in native language teaching in Finland (+3,7%), Portugal (+7,7%) and Hungary (+4%). Italy is also slightly above the average in this respect. Germany (-4,6%) and Spain (-6%), on the other hand, are far below the average.
- ...foreign language teaching is supported slightly above average by Italian and Finnish teachers using digital teaching and learning tools. The high below-average by Portuguese (-9%) and Hungarian (-4,7%) teachers are noteworthy. German teachers are slightly below the average with the indicated use.
- ...Finnish teachers are far above the average (+10,4%) when it comes to the use of digital teaching and learning tools in artistic subjects. In contrast, German and Spanish teachers are slightly below the average.

ID07: Specify the types of teaching materials you prefer to use.

For this question, teachers could choose exactly one of the following possible answers.

Tabelle X: Possible answers for question ID07

Code	Answer
A1	more digital (computer, laptop, internet) than analogue teaching aids (books, paper, pens)
A2	more analogue (books, paper, pens) than digital (computer, laptop, internet) teaching aids.
A3	digital as much as analogue teaching aids.

Tabelle X: Distribution of answers for question ID07

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	5,6	3,7	5	16,7	NA	41,9	16,7	17,3	9	11,9
A2	26,4	40,7	27,5	11,1	NA	6,5	12,5	19,8	23,9	22,6
A3	68,1	55,6	67,5	72,2	NA	51,6	70,8	63	67	65,6

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative

frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included.

Figure XW: Comparison of preferred teaching materials, by country and gender

Based on the presentation of the results in Figure XW, trends in the type of teaching and learning tools used can be seen.

It becomes clear that...

- ...both types, analog and digital teaching and learning tools, are increasingly being used for teaching.
- ...gender comparison shows that there is a slight tendency among male respondents to support teaching with digital teaching and learning tools.
- ...in contrast to the male teachers, it can be seen from the result that there is a slight tendency among female respondents to use more analogous teaching and learning tools.
- ...compared to other countries, teachers from Germany, Finland and Italy stated that they used analogue rather than digital teaching and learning tools. As in the overall picture, the use of both types (analogue and digital teaching and learning tools) predominates.
- ...in a direct comparison of the two types of teaching and learning tools, teachers from Portugal, Spain and Hungary use digital rather than analogue tools in teaching. It should be emphasised that Spanish teachers most often indicated that they used digital rather than analogue teaching and learning tools (+30%).

ID08: Which circumstances prevent the successful use of learning software/learning management systems in the classroom?

For question ID08, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers for question ID08

Code	Answer
SQ001	hardware problems (failure, malfunction)
SQ002	software problems
SQ003	problems with the Internet
SQ004	expenditure for lesson preparation
SQ005	expenditure for carrying out the lessons
SQ006	expenditure for class follow-up

Table X: Distribution of answers for question ID08

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	32,9	28,8	34,2	31,3	NA	22,7	41	31,4	32,1	31,9
SQ002	12,7	5,5	15,5	13,3	NA	7,6	10,3	11,9	11,7	11,9
SQ003	32,9	15,1	33,5	39,8	NA	33,3	28,2	28,9	33,2	31,6
SQ004	6,9	12,3	3,2	1,2	NA	13,6	5,1	8,2	5,6	6,5
SQ005	4	12,3	1,3	1,2	NA	1,5	5,1	5,2	3,1	3,7
SQ006	3,5	19,2	1,3	1,2	NA	7,6	0	5,7	4,3	4,8

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included.

Figure XW3: Comparison of hindering circumstances between countries
The presentation of the results in Figure XW3 shows which circumstances prevent successful teaching with digital teaching and learning tools in a comparison of countries and gender.
It becomes clear that...

- ...overall problems with the hardware used (31.9%) and problems with the Internet (31.6%) hinder the use of digital teaching and learning tools.
- ...a gender comparison confirms this trend, 31.2% of female teachers expect that problems with hardware make it difficult to use. Similarly, 33.2% of female teachers see problems with the Internet as an obstacle to the use of digital teaching and learning tools.
- ...in comparison with other countries, teachers from Germany, Italy, Portugal and Hungary reported problems with software as obstacles to the use of digital teaching and learning tools in addition to the expected problems with hardware and the Internet.
- ...teachers from Spain and Finland consider the third most common problem to be increased effort in the preparation of lessons.

This is the resulting ranking of the obstacles:

Table XR: Ranking of the obstacles

Nr	Obstacle	Percentage
1	hardware problems (failure, malfunction)	31,9
2	problems with the Internet	31,6
3	software problems	11,9
4	expenditure for lesson preparation	6,5
5	expenditure for class follow-up	4,8
6	expenditure for carrying out the lessons	3,7

ID09: Please select the points that would support you in the use of learning software.

For this question, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID09

Code	Answer
SQ001	IT Support (extern)
SQ002	IT Support (in-school)
SQ003	support in the execution of lessons by qualified personnel
SQ004	exchange with other teachers
SQ005	cloud with materials

SQ006	regular information events
SQ007	regular, obligatory training courses
SQ008	support of the school management / the department
SQ009	sufficient time for using learning software during school year

Table X: Distribution of answers for question ID09

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	5,5	6	7,3	5,7	NA	9,6	2,9	7	6,1	6,4
SQ002	15,8	19,8	10,6	21,9	NA	18,4	16,2	16,9	15,6	16,1
SQ003	8,5	8,6	12,8	4,8	NA	7	13,2	8,6	9,7	9,3
SQ004	17,6	16,4	14,7	21	NA	17,5	17,6	16,9	17,3	17,1
SQ005	13,2	15,5	10,6	17,1	NA	18,4	25	16,6	13,9	14,9
SQ006	9,6	6,9	7,3	9,5	NA	7	5,9	8,3	8	8,1
SQ007	10,3	4,3	16,1	3,8	NA	1,8	2,9	6	9,8	8,5
SQ008	7,7	6	12,4	7,6	NA	7,9	4,4	7	9	8,4
SQ009	11,8	16,4	8,3	8,6	NA	12,3	11,8	12,6	10,5	11,2

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included.

Figure XW: Supporting Points when using learning software differentiated by country and gender

The presentation of the results in Figure XW3 shows the points the teachers would support in the use of learning software by comparing countries and gender.

It becomes clear that...

- ...exchanges with other teachers (17.1 %) and support in school (16.1 %) were chosen most frequently.
- ...a gender comparison confirms this trend without significant differences. Only cloud with materials (SQ 003) was chosen by male teachers with 16.6% and by female teachers with 13.9%.

This is the resulting ranking for the points that would support the teachers in the use of learning software:

Table XR: Ranking of the points of support

Nr.	Support	Percentage
1	exchange with other teachers	17,1
2	IT Support (in-school)	16,1
3	cloud with materials	14,9
4	sufficient time for using learning software during school year	11,2
5	support in the execution of lessons by qualified personnel	9,3
6	regular, obligatory training courses	8,5
7	support of the school management / the department	8,4
8	regular information events	8,1
9	IT Support (extern)	6,4

ID10: Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers?

For this question the teachers had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID10

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	58,3	77,8	60,8	16,7	NA	90,3	54,2	59,3	58,3	58,7
A2	41,7	22,2	39,2	83,3	NA	9,7	45,8	40,7	41,7	41,3

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this

question were not included. A comparison of countries (see Fig. XW) reveals a more differentiated picture. Fig. X shows the distribution of the entire data set.

It can be seen from the data and the graph that the majority of teachers surveyed in their countries are familiar with special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers (on average 58.7%). The answers of the Spanish teachers, in which 90.3% of the interviewees stated that they were familiar with corresponding offers, should be emphasised, followed by the Finnish teachers (77.8%). Only the results of the Portuguese teachers did not follow this trend. 83.3% stated that there were no special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers.

ID11: Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers?

For this question the teachers had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID11

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	91,5	83,3	87,1	93,3	NA	90,3	90,9	94,2	88,6	90,7
A2	8,5	16,7	12,9	6,7	NA	9,7	9,1	5,8	11,4	9,3

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included. A comparison of countries (see Fig. XW) reveals a more differentiated picture. Fig. X shows the distribution of the entire data.

The data and the graph show that the majority of respondents would like special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers. The evaluation shows that

- ..the need for training offers is lowest in Finland (83.3%) and highest in Portugal (93.3%).
- ...male teachers (94.2%) want more continuing training than their female colleagues (88.6%).

ID12: Please select the skills you think you need to master in order to use learning software in your lessons.

For this question, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID12

Code	Answer
SQ001	editing text on the computer
SQ002	processing images on the computer
SQ003	editing videos on the computer
SQ004	using spreadsheet on the computer
SQ005	using presentation software
SQ006	doing research on the Internet
SQ007	integrating computers/ devices in a network
SQ008	dealing with networked computers/ devices
SQ009	managing accounts within a network
SQ010	structuring and administrating documents and data
SQ011	basic knowledge of data protection and copyright
SQ012	assisting students with the use of digital terminals

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID12

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	10	11,1	9,9	10,1	NA	11,2	7,4	10,6	9,9	10,1
SQ002	10,6	6,3	8,9	11,1	NA	10,7	11,1	10	9,6	9,7
SQ003	6,2	2,1	7,4	9,5	NA	8	17,3	6,1	7,8	7,2
SQ004	9,8	2,6	6,6	8,5	NA	6,4	7,4	8,9	6,5	7,3
SQ005	10,4	5,8	14	11,1	NA	9,1	17,3	10,4	11,4	11,1
SQ006	11,9	12,1	14,2	9	NA	10,2	2,5	11,7	11,3	11,4
SQ007	6,6	11,6	2,8	8,5	NA	7,5	6,2	6,7	6,5	6,6
SQ008	6,4	10,5	9,7	9	NA	8,6	7,4	7,4	9	8,4
SQ009	4,5	8,9	3,8	2,6	NA	4,3	3,7	3,9	4,9	4,6

SQ010	7,4	7,9	6,1	5,3	NA	8	1,2	7	6,3	6,6
SQ011	7,2	9,5	5,1	6,3	NA	9,6	3,7	8,3	6,2	6,9
SQ012	9,1	11,6	11,5	9	NA	6,4	14,8	9,1	10,5	10

Table X shows the distribution of answers as relative frequencies in percent, differentiated by country and gender. When calculating the relative frequencies in Table X, the cases in which no answer was given to this question were not included. A comparison of countries (see Fig. XW) reveals a more differentiated picture.

It becomes clear that...

- ...doing research on the Internet (11,4 %), using presentation software (11,1%), editing text on the computer (10,1%) and assisting students with the use of digital terminals (10,0 %) are the most frequently chosen skills that teachers think they need to master in order to use learning software in their lessons.
- ...there is no noticeable difference when differentiating by gender.

Table XR shows the resulting ranking for the skills that teachers need to master in order to use learning software in their lessons.

Table XR: Skills for teachers

Nr.	Support	Percentage
1	doing research on the Internet	11,4
2	using presentation software	11,1
3	editing text on the computer	10,1
4	assisting students with the use of digital terminals	10,0
5	processing images on the computer	9,7
6	dealing with networked computers/ devices	8,4
7	using spreadsheet on the computer	7,3
8	editing videos on the computer	7,2
9	basic knowledge of data protection and copyright	6,9
10	structuring and administrating documents and data	6,6
10	integrating computers/ devices in a network	6,6
11	managing accounts within a network	4,6

ID13: Please assess your skills in working with the computer.

ID13 was measured on a four-point Likert scale (very good - good - mediocre - bad). If a respondent could not rate an item, "do not know" could be selected. The scale values were coded in this order with the numbers from 1 to 4.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID13

Code	Answer
SQ001	I can write and format a text.
SQ002	I can edit an image.
SQ003	I can edit a video.
SQ004	I can process data with a spreadsheet.
SQ005	I can research and store information on the internet
SQ006	I can create a presentation.
SQ007	I can use different browsers.
SQ008	I can use different platforms on the Internet.
SQ009	I can securely handle my personal data and passwords on the Internet.
SQ010	I can handle subject-specific learning software.
SQ011	I can use different multimedia objects (pictures, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation.
SQ012	I can display data in diagrams.
SQ013	I know legal basics (data protection, copyright)
SQ014	I can guide students in learning with digital devices.
SQ015	I can structure and manage digital content (data and files)

Table X shows a summary of the data. Based on the assumption that the characteristics SQ001 to SQ015 are in fact interval scaled, the weighted arithmetic averages were formed based on the above-mentioned coding of the responses. In addition, the table shows the total mean value (AVG) as the mean value of the data for the individual countries and the standard deviation (STD) of the mean values.

A classification according to female and male teachers is provided as well.

Table X: Summary of answers to question ID13

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	AVG	STD	□□	□□
SQ001	1,76	1,62	2,11	1,46	NA	1,67	1,5	1,69	0,24	1,67	1,84

SQ002	2,18	2,73	2,5	1,9	NA	2,24	1,92	2,25	0,33	2,09	2,37
SQ003	2,71	3,41	2,89	2,23	NA	2,63	3,04	2,82	0,4	2,68	2,86
SQ004	2,21	2,76	2,76	2,17	NA	2,16	2,04	2,35	0,32	2,19	2,49
SQ005	1,75	1,77	2,22	1,63	NA	1,81	1,17	1,72	0,34	1,67	1,89
SQ006	2	1,83	2,63	1,97	NA	1,95	2,25	2,1	0,29	1,89	2,31
SQ007	1,79	1,69	2,49	2,13	NA	1,81	1,33	1,87	0,39	1,75	2,08
SQ008	1,94	2,38	2,56	2,13	NA	1,95	1,38	2,06	0,41	2,01	2,2
SQ009	2,07	2,12	2,42	2,17	NA	2,22	1,29	2,05	0,39	2,04	2,17
SQ010	2,17	2,19	2,67	2,28	NA	2,4	2	2,28	0,23	2,24	2,39
SQ011	2,27	2,4	2,54	2,3	NA	2,04	2,22	2,29	0,17	2,21	2,39
SQ012	2,15	2,67	2,9	2,27	NA	2,4	2,61	2,5	0,28	2,23	2,62
SQ013	2,33	2,41	2,78	2,28	NA	2,73	2,43	2,49	0,21	2,47	2,54
SQ014	2,18	2,33	2,65	2,39	NA	2,44	1,96	2,33	0,24	2,17	2,45
SQ015	2,13	2,48	2,47	2,32	NA	2,48	2,25	2,36	0,15	2,21	2,39
AVG	2,11	2,32	2,57	2,11	NA	2,2	1,96	2,21	0,21	2,26	2,61
STD	0,25	0,48	0,22	0,26	NA	0,32	0,54	0,3		0,27	0,27

The following network diagrams were used to visualize the data. The characteristic of each item is shown for each country. For comparison purposes, the given mean value (AVG column) of the mean values of all countries is also displayed.

It's conspicuous that...

- ...the values of the interviewed Finnish teachers for the Item "I can write and format a text" are below average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Italian teachers for the most Items are below average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Portuguese teachers for the Items "I can write and format a text", "I can edit an image", "I can edit a video" and "I can process data with a spreadsheet" are above average.

- ...the values of the interviewed Spanish teachers for the Items “I can edit a video” and “I can use different multimedia objects (pictures, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation” are above average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Hungarian teachers for the most Items are above average
- ...almost all answers from male teachers are above average.
- ...almost all answers from the female teachers are below average.

ID14: Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students?

While the questions ID05 to ID13 were primarily intended to survey barriers and competences on the part of teachers with regard to the use of digital tools in teaching, the questionnaire for the necessary competences begins with ID14. For this question the teachers had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID14

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	45,1	48,1	44,9	15,6	NA	71	62,5	50	44,5	46,4
A2	54,9	51,9	55,1	84,4	NA	29	37,5	50	55,5	53,6

The graph and Table XE show that there are different opinions on the existence of special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students. A total of 46.4% of all teachers surveyed said they knew about corresponding offers for students and 53.6% said they did not. There were deviations from this trend in the results of the Portuguese, Spanish and Hungarian teachers surveyed. For example, 71% of Spanish teachers and 62.5% of Hungarian teachers surveyed indicated that they were aware of corresponding offers for pupils. Contrary to the general trend, 15.6% of Portuguese teachers said they were aware of such offers.

ID15: Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students?

For this question the teachers had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table XE: Distribution of answers to the question ID15

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	94,8	78,6	88,4	92,6	NA	77,8	88,9	90	90	90
A2	5,2	21,4	11,6	7,4	NA	22,2	11,1	10	10	10

The graph and table XE show that there is a demand for special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students. In total, 90% of all interviewed teachers agree. There are slight deviations to that trend, most notably on the part of Finnish teachers with 78.6% and Spanish teachers with 77.8%.

ID16: Select the points you identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/learning management systems.

For this question, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID16

Code	Answer
SQ001	Diverse devices (BYOD - Bring your own device)
SQ002	Complex software structure
SQ003	Complicated operation of the learning software
SQ004	Lack of communication between teachers and parents
SQ005	Lack of communication between school management and parents
SQ006	Lack of information about the use of the learning software for parents
SQ007	Lack of skills in the use of a computer
SQ008	Lack of internet skills
SQ009	Lack of skills in dealing with internet-based / browser-based software

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID16

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	14,2	13	10,9	9,6	NA	14,3	14	15,7	11,2	12,5
SQ002	12,5	14,5	13,5	15,7	NA	11,2	12,3	12,4	13,5	13,2
SQ003	7,4	13	4,8	8,4	NA	14,3	5,3	8,6	7,6	8
SQ004	14,2	2,9	5,7	6	NA	14,3	7	11,4	7,8	8,8
SQ005	8,5	1,4	4,8	1,2	NA	11,2	7	8,1	5,2	6
SQ006	11,4	8,7	14,8	16,9	NA	13,3	29,8	13,3	15,1	14,6
SQ007	17,6	23,2	21,7	13,3	NA	10,2	12,3	15,7	18,3	17,5
SQ008	5,7	8,7	10,4	13,3	NA	7,1	5,3	7,1	9,2	8,6
SQ009	8,5	14,5	13,5	15,7	NA	4,1	7	7,6	12,2	10,8

It becomes clear that...

- ... the lack of skills in the use of a computer (17,5%), lack of information about the use of the learning software for parents (14,6%), complex software structure (13,2%), diverse devices (BYOD - Bring your own device) (12,5%) and the lack of skill in dealing with internet-based/ browser-based software (10,8%) are the five most frequently chosen points that teachers identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/learning management systems.
- ...there is no noticeable difference when differentiating by gender.

Table XR shows the resulting ranking for the skills that teachers identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/ learning management systems.

Table XR: Barriers for students

Nr.	Support	Percentage
1	Lack of skills in the use of a computer	17,5
2	Lack of information about the use of the learning software for parents	14,6
3	Complex software structure	13,2
4	Diverse devices (BYOD - Bring your own device)	12,5
5	Lack of skills in dealing with internet-based/ browser-based software	10,8
6	Lack of communication between teachers and parents	8,8
7	Lack of internet skills	8,6
8	Complicated operation of the learning software	8,0
9	Lack of information about the use of the learning software for the parents	6,0

ID17: Specify what skills students need to have to successfully participate in lessons with learning software/learning management systems.

For this question, teachers could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID17

Code	Answer
SQ001	reading
SQ002	writing
SQ003	editing text on the computer
SQ004	processing images on the computer
SQ005	editing videos on the computer
SQ006	using spreadsheets on the computer
SQ007	using presentation software
SQ008	doing research on the internet
SQ009	manage data and files
SQ010	programming in a programming language
SQ011	working with a partner
SQ012	working in groups
SQ013	creating web pages

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question ID17

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	15,8	20,7	17	14,5	NA	15,4	17,4	14,4	17,6	16,5
SQ002	12,5	18,1	14,1	13,9	NA	12,2	12,8	12,8	14,1	13,6
SQ003	13,6	14,7	11,2	11	NA	12,2	12,8	14	11,7	12,5
SQ004	7,2	6	6,2	10,4	NA	9,6	9,2	7,8	7,8	7,8
SQ005	5	1,7	4,7	7,5	NA	7,7	0,9	5,5	4,7	5
SQ006	6,6	5,2	5,1	9,2	NA	7,1	8,3	7,3	6,3	6,7
SQ007	11,4	6	9,8	12,1	NA	10,3	11	10,8	10,2	10,4
SQ008	16,3	15,5	17,4	12,7	NA	13,5	14,7	15,8	15,3	15,4
SQ009	11,6	12,1	14,5	8,7	NA	12,2	12,8	11,7	12,4	12,1
SQ010	4,4	0	5,1	5,8	NA	3,8	1,8	3,9	4,1	4
SQ011	11,6	12,9	10,1	7,5	NA	8,3	10,1	9,8	10,5	10,2
SQ012	12,2	9,5	14,5	9,2	NA	14,1	13,8	11,2	13,2	12,4
SQ013	2,2	0	4	2,3	NA	3,2	1,8	2,7	2,4	2,5

It becomes clear that...

- ...reading (16,5%), doing research on the internet (15,4%) and writing (13,6%) are considered to be the most important skills for students to learn successfully with learning software/learning management systems. Least important are considered to be programming in a programming language (4,0%) and creating web pages (2,5%).
- ...there is no noteworthy difference in the answers of the different countries. The range in the data per answer is between 3,7% (SQ003) and 6,8% (SQ005).
- ...there is no noticeable difference when differentiating by gender.

This is the resulting ranking for the skills that teachers identify as barriers for students to learn successfully with learning software/ learning management systems.

Table XR: Necessary skills for students when using leartech

Nr.	Skill	Percentage
1	reading	16,5
2	doing research on the internet	15,4
3	writing	13,6
4	editing text on the computer	12,5
5	working in groups	12,4
6	manage data and files	12,1
7	using presentation software	10,4
8	working with a partner	10,2
9	processing images on the computer	7,8
10	using spreadsheets on the computer	6,7
11	editing videos on the computer	5,0
12	programming in a programming language	4,0
13	creating web pages	2,5

ID18: How important are the following computer skills for students to use learning software?

ID18 was measured on a four-point Likert scale (very good - good - mediocre - bad). If a respondent could not rate an item, "do not know" could be selected. The scale values were coded in this order with the numbers from 1 to 4.

Table X: Possible answers to question ID18

Code	Answer
SQ001	Students can write and format a text.
SQ002	Students can edit an image.
SQ003	Students can edit a video.
SQ004	Students can process data with a spreadsheet.
SQ005	Students can research and store information on the Internet
SQ006	Students can create a presentation.
SQ007	Students can use different browsers.
SQ008	Students can use browser-based / internet-based software
SQ009	Students can use different platforms on the Internet.
SQ010	Students can securely handle personal data and passwords on the Internet.
SQ011	Students can use different multimedia objects (images, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation.
SQ012	Students can display data in diagrams.
SQ013	Students can create web pages.
SQ014	Students can program in a programming language

Table X shows a summary of the data. Based on the assumption that the characteristics SQ001 to SQ014 are in fact interval scaled, the weighted arithmetic averages were formed based on the above-mentioned coding of the responses. In addition, the table shows the total mean value (AVG) as the mean value of the data for the individual countries and the standard deviation (STD) of the mean values.

A classification according to female and male teachers is provided as well.

Table X: Summary of answers to question ID18

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	AVG	STD	□□	□□
SQ001	1,66	1,78	1,89	1,45	NA	2,05	1,29	1,69	0,28	1,61	1,75
SQ002	2,3	2,58	2,23	1,97	NA	2,16	1,83	2,18	0,26	2,12	2,26
SQ003	2,82	3,12	2,52	2,13	NA	2,28	2,48	2,56	0,36	2,62	2,58
SQ004	2,2	3,08	2,47	2,13	NA	2,58	1,79	2,38	0,44	2,24	2,41
SQ005	1,67	1,65	1,94	1,73	NA	1,59	1,08	1,61	0,28	1,59	1,71
SQ006	2,06	1,96	2,25	1,64	NA	2,24	1,88	2,01	0,23	1,86	2,15
SQ007	2,3	2,12	2,29	1,9	NA	2,32	1,17	2,02	0,45	2,14	2,1
SQ008	2,1	2,12	2,22	1,93	NA	2,33	1,39	2,01	0,33	2,01	2,09
SQ009	2,21	2,23	2,4	1,97	NA	2,16	1,36	2,06	0,37	2,13	2,17
SQ010	1,61	1,74	1,95	1,46	NA	1,65	1,21	1,61	0,25	1,53	1,73
SQ011	2,2	1,96	2,32	1,87	NA	2,2	1,74	2,05	0,23	2,03	2,17
SQ012	2,38	2,75	2,52	2,29	NA	2,56	2,3	2,47	0,18	2,31	2,53
SQ013	3,06	3,17	2,73	2,47	NA	2,77	2,7	2,81	0,26	3	2,77
SQ014	3,08	3,24	2,6	2,4	NA	2,77	2,71	2,8	0,31	2,95	2,75
AVG*	2,26	2,39	2,31	1,95	NA	2,26	1,78	2,16	0,24	2,26	2,61
STD	0,47	0,58	0,25	0,32	NA	0,35	0,57	0,4		0,44	0,35

The following network diagrams were used to visualize the data. The characteristic of each item is shown for each country. For comparison purposes, the given mean value (AVG column) of the mean values of all countries is also displayed.

It's conspicuous that...

- ...the values of the interviewed German teachers for the Item "Students can edit a video", "Students can use different browsers", "Students can create web pages" and "Students can program in a programming language" are below average.

- ...the values of the interviewed Finnish teachers for the Items “Students can edit an image”, “Students can edit a video”, “Students can process data with a spreadsheet”, “Students can create web pages” and “Students can program in a programming language” are below average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Italian teachers for the most Items are below the average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Portuguese teachers for the most Items are above average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Spanish teachers for the Items “Students can write and format a text”, “Students can create a presentation”, “Students can use different browsers” and “Students can use browser-based/ internet-based on the Internet” are below average. For the Item “Students can edit a video” the values are above average.
- ...the values of the interviewed Hungarian teachers for the all Items are above average

Deutschland

Annex 5: Answers to Survey Questions (Students)

IDS06: Specify the average number of hours per day you use these devices.

Question IDS06 asked students to rate different items on a 5-step Likert scale, where 1 = "less than 2 hours", 2 = "between 2 and 4 hours", 3 = "between 4 and 6 hours", 4 = "between 6 and 8 hours", 5 = "more than 8 hours". The following items should be evaluated.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS06

Code	Answer
SQ001	TV
SQ002	computer
SQ003	transportable computer (notebook / tablet)
SQ004	smartphone
SQ005	mobile phone
SQ006	radio
SQ007	MP3-Player
SQ008	E-Book Reader
SQ009	game console
SQ010	language assistance system (for example Alexa, GoogleNow, Siri etc)

Table X shows a summary of the data. Based on the assumption that the characteristics SQ001 to SQ010 are in fact interval scaled, the weighted arithmetic averages were formed based on the above-mentioned coding of the responses. In addition, the table shows the total mean value (AVG) as the mean value of the data for the individual countries and the standard deviation (STD) of the mean values.

A classification according to female and male teachers is provided as well.

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS06

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	AVG	STD	□□	□□
SQ001	2,11	1,7	2,51	1,76	NA	1,42	1,41	1,82	0,43	2,03	1,89
SQ002	1,87	1,71	1,78	1,56	NA	1,29	1,34	1,59	0,24	1,81	1,65
SQ003	1,75	1,61	1,83	1,53	NA	1,76	1,32	1,63	0,19	1,68	1,67
SQ004	4,01	3,51	3,86	2,16	NA	2,29	1,76	2,93	0,98	3,46	3,51
SQ005	2,86	1,08	2,78	2,6	NA	1,42	1,22	1,99	0,84	2,38	2,36
SQ006	1,76	1,31	1,41	1,11	NA	1,09	1,23	1,32	0,25	1,51	1,59
SQ007	1,5	1,14	1,6	1,18	NA	1,2	1,08	1,28	0,21	1,35	1,42
SQ008	1,42	1,14	1,83	1,04	NA	1,22	1,06	1,28	0,3	1,37	1,34
SQ009	1,5	1,83	2,71	1,56	NA	2	1,4	1,83	0,48	1,89	1,41
SQ010	1,94	1,06	2,15	1,09	NA	1,4	1,02	1,44	0,49	1,72	1,64
AVG	2,07	1,61	2,25	1,56	NA	1,51	1,28	1,71	0,37	2,26	2,61
STD	0,8	0,73	0,74	0,51	NA	0,39	0,22	0,5		0,6	0,66

The following network diagrams were used to visualize the data. The characteristic of each item is shown for each country. For comparison purposes, the given mean value (AVG column) of the mean values of all countries is also displayed.

It's conspicuous that...

- ...when averaging about all devices and countries the average is 1,71. The students are therefore spending a little less than 2 hours per week on each device.
- ...answer SQ004 (smartphone) has a significantly higher average over all than the rest of the items (2,93). When ranking the devices by average AVG the runner up is SQ005 (mobile phone) with an overall average of 1,99.
- ...those two answers are also the ones with the highest standard deviation of 0,98 and 0,84 respectively.
- ...SQ004 is also the highest ranking in every country but Portugal.
- ...Italy has the highest average per country when using the mentioned devices (2,25), while Hungary has the lowest (1,28).

- ...German students have the highest standard deviation in the average usage frequency of the different devices (0,8) while Hungarian students have the lowest (0,22).
- ...SQ007 (MP3-Player) and SQ008 (E-Book Reader) are on average used the least amount of time (both 1,28).
- ...female students use the mentioned digital devices slightly more frequent than the male ones (AVG: 2,61 to 2,51).

IDS07: Can your parents help you with problems with these devices?

For this question, students could choose exactly one of the following possible answers.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS07

Code	Answer
A1	Yes
A2	No
A3	I help my parents.
A4	We help each other.
A5	I don't need any help.

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS07

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	19,5	17,5	44,2	22,2	NA	22,2	12,6	18,5	23,2	20,8
A2	18,2	7,8	8,1	13,3	NA	4,4	2,4	14,9	11,7	13,3
A3	19,5	29,1	2,3	28,9	NA	4,4	9,4	18,9	15,9	17,4
A4	21,4	27,2	22,1	26,7	NA	51,1	56,7	27,3	29,3	28,3
A5	21,4	18,4	23,3	8,9	NA	17,8	18,9	20,5	19,9	20,2

Table XR shows the resulting ranking of the items from the question. Most students answered that they help each other and that their parents can help them. Approximately $\frac{1}{5}$ of the students said, that they don't need any help with problems with devices.

Table X: Ranking help by relative frequency

Nr.	Item	Percentage
1	We help each other	28,3
2	Yes	20,8
3	I don't need any help	20,2
4	I help my parents	17,4
5	No	13,3

IDS08: Indicate how often the computer/ laptop or mobile devices are used in class each week.

For this question, students could choose exactly one of the following possible answers.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS08

Code	Answer
A1	not at all
A2	less than 2 times
A3	between 2 and 4 times
A4	between 4 and 6 times
A5	between 6 and 8 times
A6	more than 8 times

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS08

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	23,9	1	18,8	13,3	NA	28,9	6,3	19,3	17,6	18,5
A2	17,4	4,9	23,5	42,2	NA	35,6	39,4	22,1	20,8	21,5
A3	20,4	32,4	29,4	31,1	NA	17,8	29,9	22,7	25,4	24
A4	17,5	22,5	10,6	4,4	NA	4,4	3,1	15,7	13	14,4
A5	10,7	15,7	10,6	0	NA	4,4	2,4	8	10,7	9,3
A6	10,2	23,5	7,1	8,9	NA	8,9	18,9	12,1	12,6	12,3

From the data and the graphical representation it becomes clear that...

- ...laptop, computer or mobile devices are used in class less than 2 times a week.
- ...the Finnish students most often state that laptop, computer or mobile devices are used between 2 and 4 times a week.

IDS09: Are there special information events or training hours for the introduction of new learning software/ learning management systems for students?

On this question, students had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS09

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	69,5	55,9	62,4	73,3	NA	68,9	57,5	64	68,1	66
A2	30,5	44,1	37,6	26,7	NA	31,1	42,5	36	31,9	34

The diagram and Table X show that there are different opinions on the existence of special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students. A total of 66,0% of all students surveyed said they knew about

corresponding offers for students. There is a noticeable deviation from this average in some countries. The biggest difference is visible in Finland (A1: -10,1%) and Portugal (A1: +7,3%). The range in the data is therefore 17,4%.

IDS10: Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of new learning software/ learning management systems for students?

On this question, students had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS10

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	79,6	40	90,6	83,3	NA	92,9	87	78,9	78	78,5
A2	20,4	60	9,4	16,7	NA	7,1	13	21,1	22	21,5

The graph and table X show that there generally is a demand for special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for students. In total, 78,5% of all interviewed students state that there should be. There are slight deviations to that trend. A substantial difference becomes visible in Finland, where 40% of students chose A1 (-38,5% to average). The biggest positive difference is visible in Spain (+14,4%).

IDS11: Should there be special information events or training sessions for the introduction of new learning software for teachers?

On this question, students had to choose between the options "Yes" (A1) and "No" (A2).

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS11

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	83,7	61,8	88,2	84,4	NA	80	85,8	80,7	83,2	81,9
A2	16,3	38,2	11,8	15,6	NA	20	14,2	19,3	16,8	18,1

The graph and table X show that the students assess, that there is a need for special information events or training sessions for the introduction of learning software/learning management systems for teachers. In total, 81,9% of all interviewed students state that there should be corresponding courses. There are slight deviations to that trend. A substantial difference becomes visible in Finland, where 61,8% of students chose A1 (-20,1% to average). The biggest positive difference is visible in Italy (+6,3%).

IDS12: Indicate which learning materials you prefer to use.

Bei dieser Frage konnten die Schüler aus den folgenden Antwortmöglichkeiten genau eine auswählen.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS12

Code	Answer
A1	more digital (computer, laptop, internet) than analogue teaching aids (books, paper, pens)
A2	more analogue (books, paper, pens) than digital (computer, laptop, internet) teaching aids.
A3	digital as much as analogue teaching aids.

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS12

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
A1	43	10,8	38,8	31,1	NA	33,3	34,6	40	34,2	37,2
A2	14,9	54,9	14,1	8,9	NA	8,9	9,4	13,7	22	17,8
A3	42,1	34,3	47,1	60	NA	57,8	55,9	46,3	43,8	45,1

Based on the presentation of the results in Figure X, trends in the type of teaching and learning tools used can be seen.

It becomes clear that...

- ...over all students prefer a mix of digital and analogue teaching tools (45,1%) before digital (37,2%).
- ...male students prefer pure digital tools slightly more than female ones (+5,8%). The same is true for a mix of both (+2,5%).
- ...only Finnish students prefer pure analogue teaching tools (54,9%; +37,1% to average)

IDS13: What do you need to know to work with learning software?

For this question, students could choose from the following answer options. Multiple choices were possible.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS13

Code	Answer
SQ001	reading
SQ002	writing
SQ003	editing text on the computer
SQ004	processing images on the computer
SQ005	editing videos on the computer
SQ006	using spreadsheet on the computer
SQ007	using presentation software
SQ008	doing research on the internet
SQ009	managing files and data
SQ010	working with a partner
SQ011	working in groups
SQ012	creating web pages

Table X: Distribution of answers to the question IDS13

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	□□	□□	□
SQ001	13,7	15,4	8	11	NA	10,7	14	13,1	13,4	13,3
SQ002	11,9	13,9	6,6	10,7	NA	8,3	11,1	11,4	11,6	11,5
SQ003	10,8	10,9	11	8,2	NA	10,3	9,9	10,6	10,5	10,5
SQ004	6,5	6,2	7,5	8,5	NA	9,1	7	7	6,7	6,8
SQ005	4,9	1	10,8	5,8	NA	8,7	6,1	5,3	5,2	5,2
SQ006	4,6	4	5,2	3,7	NA	5	6,9	4,8	5	4,9

SQ007	7,7	5,7	9,1	9,1	NA	10,3	7,3	7,4	8	7,7
SQ008	12,6	11,7	11,6	12,5	NA	9,9	11,6	12,7	11,6	12,2
SQ009	7	7,9	5,8	6,7	NA	8,7	7,9	7	7,4	7,2
SQ010	7	10	4,7	9,5	NA	6,2	7	7,4	7,2	7,3
SQ011	8,2	10,5	7,7	10,1	NA	6,6	7	8,2	8,4	8,3
SQ012	4,9	2,9	11,9	4,3	NA	6,2	4,1	5,1	5	5,1

It becomes clear that...

- ...reading (13,3%), doing research on the internet (12,2%), writing (11,5%), editing text with the computer (10,5%) and working in groups (8,3%) are the five most frequently indicated items, that students need to know to work with with learning software.
- ...the items "creating web pages" (5,1%) and "using spreadsheet on the computer" (4,9%), are chosen the least.
- ...a gender comparison confirms this trend without significant differences.

IDS14: Please assess your skills in working with the computer.

IDS14 was measured on a four-point Likert scale (very good - good - mediocre - bad). If a respondent could not rate an item, "do not know" could be selected. The scale values were coded in this order with the numbers from 1 to 4.

Table X: Possible answers to question IDS14

Code	Answer
SQ001	I can write and format a text.
SQ002	I can edit an image.
SQ003	I can edit a video.
SQ004	I can process data with a spreadsheet.
SQ005	I can research and store information on the internet.
SQ006	I can create a presentation.
SQ007	I can use different browsers.
SQ008	I can use different platforms on the internet.
SQ009	I can securely handle my personal data and passwords on the internet.
SQ010	I can use different multimedia objects (pictures, videos, audio tracks) in a presentation.
SQ011	I can create web pages.
SQ012	I can display data in diagrams.

Table X shows a summary of the data. Based on the assumption that the characteristics SQ001 to SQ012 are in fact interval scaled, the weighted arithmetic averages were formed based on the above-mentioned coding of the responses. In addition, the table shows the total mean value (AVG) as the mean value of the data for the individual countries and the standard deviation (STD) of the mean values.

A classification according to female and male teachers is provided as well.

Table X: Summary of answers to question IDS14

Code	DE	FI	IT	PT	SE	ES	HU	AVG	STD	□□	□□
SQ001	1,86	1,65	1,96	1,21	NA	1,77	1,44	1,65	0,28	1,79	1,72
SQ002	1,85	2,02	1,88	1,5	NA	1,57	1,7	1,75	0,2	1,83	1,82
SQ003	2,25	2,26	2,03	2,12	NA	1,97	2,31	2,16	0,14	2,22	2,23
SQ004	2,29	2,45	2,41	1,94	NA	2,14	2,29	2,25	0,19	2,28	2,31
SQ005	1,56	1,7	1,5	1,43	NA	1,43	1,48	1,52	0,1	1,51	1,58
SQ006	2,09	1,66	2,17	1,26	NA	1,56	2,71	1,91	0,52	2,14	1,99
SQ007	1,68	1,7	1,76	1,68	NA	1,54	1,32	1,61	0,16	1,61	1,66
SQ008	1,9	2,05	1,63	1,42	NA	1,55	1,77	1,72	0,23	1,81	1,87
SQ009	1,69	1,65	1,51	1,18	NA	1,79	1,45	1,54	0,22	1,64	1,59
SQ010	1,95	1,78	1,88	1,48	NA	1,6	2,24	1,82	0,27	1,92	1,93
SQ011	2,12	2,53	2,34	2,61	NA	2,7	2,93	2,54	0,28	2,3	2,4
SQ012	2,1	2,26	2,68	2,03	NA	2,18	2,73	2,33	0,3	2,26	2,25
AVG*	1,94	1,98	1,98	1,65	NA	1,82	2,03	1,9	0,14	1,94	1,95
STD	0,23	0,33	0,37	0,44	NA	0,37	0,57	0,34		0,29	0,29

The following network diagrams were used to visualize the data. The characteristic of each item is shown for each country. For comparison purposes, the given mean value (AVG column) of the mean values of all countries is also displayed.

It's conspicuous that...

- ...when averaging about all devices and countries the average is 1,90. The students are therefore evaluating their skills for working with the computer approximately as good.
- ... the answers SQ005 (I can research and store information on the internet) and SQ009 (I can securely handle my personal data and passwords on the internet) have over all the best rating (AVG 1,52 and 1,54 respectively).
- ...SQ005 is also the answer with the lowest standard deviation.

- ...all countries have a similar average (standard deviation 0,14). Portugal differs most significantly from the overall average (1,65; -0,25)
- ...SQ012 (I can display data in diagrams) and SQ011 (I can create web pages) are the lowest rated skills (2,26 and 2,3 respectively)
- ...the highest deviation (0,52) occurs with item SQ006 (I can create a presentation).
- ...Hungarian students have the highest deviation in their skill assessment (0,57), German students the lowest (0,23).
- ...male and female students have about the same average (1,94 and 1,95) and the same deviation (both 0,29)

